
WORK PLACE CENTRALITY AND COUNTERPRODUCTIVE WORK BEHAVIOUR IN BAYELSA STATE CIVIL SERVICE

By

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ABSTRACT

This paper looked into the correlations between workplace centrality and counterproductive work behaviour in Bayelsa State civil service. Organizational behaviour literature has addressed and presented multi-factor that are considered predictor of counter productive work behaviour. These research efforts notwithstanding, it is observed that none of the studies were conducted in the public sector particularly amongst civil servants in Bayelsa state. The study adopts a correlational investigation as it aims to establish the relationship between work centrality and counterproductive work behavior. The population of the Civil Servants for each of the Ministries was obtained from the State Civil Service Commission and further verified from the Establishment Unit of each ministry. The population of this study therefore is 1978. The Krejcie and Morgan (1980) sample size determination table is used and this gave a sample size of 332. The assessment of the study's reliability was conducted utilizing the Cronbach's alpha statistical procedure. The results obtained from the SPSS-assisted analysis utilizing the Spearman rank correlation technique indicate a negative correlation between the dimensions of workplace centrality; task passion, dutifulness and counterproductive work behaviour. The study found a strong and significant correlation between workplace centrality and counterproductive work behavior. Among other recommendations, Administrators in the Civil Service should actively encourage and foster a culture that values and promotes task passion among employees. This can be achieved through leadership support, recognition of passionate efforts, and creating an environment where employees feel a sense of purpose in their work.

Keywords: *Workplace centrality, task passion, dutifulness, counterproductive work behavior, civil service*

INTRODUCTION

There is a deluge of organisational efforts to guarantee and maximise workforce productivity in order to accomplish targeted outcomes. Scholarly concerns about divergent work behaviour that hinders the firm's ability to accomplish its aims have also been raised by this purpose (Akala & Gabrielson, 2010; Elomi et al., 2014). The worry over ineffective work practices has grown exponentially. This is due to the rising prevalence of counterproductive work behaviour, which in turn hinders the achievement of certain organisational objectives. Menser and Schaffer (2013) have argued that counterproductive work behavior has important economic, sociological and psychological implication both for the individual and organization. Bennett and Robinson (2000) gave example of counterproductive work behavior to include gossiping, poor communication practices, sabotage, withdrawal, harassment and drug use. These are considered costly at whatever level of analysis because they invariably contravene set organizational norms and variance with ethical practices and procedures

So far, much of the extant positions on predictions of counterproductive work behaviour have been attributed to work climate and managerial behaviours that are considered to have reduced the administrative and operational spheres of employees. Akang (2016) observed that the civil service sector has evolved rapidly considering increase in globalization practices and government policies targeted at improving on revenue generation. This has also signaled increased work responsibilities on the workforce which requires moral commitment behaviour.

While the theoretical and empirical search lasts on determinants of counterproductive work behaviour, work centrality may be seen as having the potential for predicting counterproductive work behaviour. Workplace centrality is the point at which an individual's uniqueness, priorities, and daily obligations are shaped by their place of employment. The behaviour, motivation, and engagement of employees are significantly influenced by it (Paullay, et al., 1994). While people with low workplace centrality may see work as a means to a goal rather than a defining feature of who they are, individuals with high workplace centrality may place work above other facets of their lives and find meaning and fulfilment in their employment.

The relationship between workplace centrality and counterproductive work behaviours (CWBs) is a crucial consideration. CWBs are behaviours that impair organisational performance, such as absenteeism, sabotage, workplace deviance, and interpersonal disputes (Spector & Fox, 2005). Studies indicate that CWBs may be linked to both extraordinarily high and extremely low workplace centrality. Due to a lack of commitment to their work, employees with low workplace centrality may participate in CWBs, which can result in disengagement, absenteeism, or even acts of sabotage (Marcus & Schuler, 2004). On the other hand, those who have high workplace centrality may form undesirable work behaviours that cause tension, annoyance, and retaliatory actions when they feel their efforts are not appreciated or are being hindered (Bolino, et al., 2010).

The workforce is expected to operationalise many of the strategic approaches and alternatives as firm competition increases. Their behaviour is rapidly shifting from support as a means of leveraging skills and competency gaps to poor commitment and a lack of willingness to show support for one another. Organizational behaviour literature have addressed and presented multi-factor that are considered predictor of counter productive work behavior. For instance,

Miebach and Kluge (2014) examined personality traits as predictor of deviant behavior of employees. The study result showed self-control correlates with avoidance of gossiping behaviour a component of counterproductive work behavior. Ibama and Ibama (2019) investigated the relationship between human capital development and employee counterproductive work behavior and the result showed a significant relationship in the banking sector. In same vein, Enabuile and Jerome (2018) had examined the relationship between work centrality and counterproductive work behavior in the banking sector in Nairobi. The study results showed a weak but significant relationship.

These research efforts notwithstanding, it is observed that none of the studies were conducted in the public sector particularly amongst civil servants. All of these constitute research gaps especially in the light of contextual difference in practices and work cultures. Against this backdrop, this study is aimed at investigating the empirical link between work centrality and counterproductive work behaviour.

AIM OF THE PAPER

This paper seeks to explore the empirical link between work centrality and counterproductive workplace behavior, shedding light on their intricate relationship.

The specific objectives are to;

1. Investigate the relationship between task passion and counterproductive work behavior within the civil service in Bayelsa State.
2. Explore the link between dutifulness and counterproductive work behavior in the civil service in Bayelsa State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research is guided by the following research questions:

1. Does a relationship exist between task passion and counterproductive work behavior in the civil service of Bayelsa State?
2. Is there a connection between dutifulness and counterproductive work behavior in the civil service of Bayelsa State?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between task passion and lateness in the civil service in Bayelsa State

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between task passion and absenteeism in the the civil service in Bayelsa State

THEORITICAL UNDERPINING

The Social Exchange Theory (SET) (Blau, 1964)

The theory of social exchange was first put out by Blau (1964). It is seen to be a powerful paradigm for analysing any human exchange relationships, and it holds that a subjective cost-benefit analysis is used to establish human interactions. The underlying assumptions of this theory are that people typically repeat behaviours that have previously earned them rewards and that the more times an activity has produced a reward, the more probable it is that the person would repeat that behaviour (Homans, 1958).

The foundation for a critical understanding of workplace behaviour is provided by the SET, which pointed out that social relationships are founded on the belief that acts of kindness will be returned (Blau, 1964).

In the meta-analysis by Colquitt et al. (2013), Social Exchange Theory (SET) emerged as the most commonly utilized framework, highlighting its significance in explaining workplace behaviors through reciprocal relationships between employees and organizations. It is best known for analysing employees' responses to justice, fairness, and equity. Social exchange as a form of interpersonal relationship has been the subject of numerous organisational studies over the past ten years, primarily based on Blau's (1964) theories. The meta-analysis's findings indicate that social exchange indicators and justice dimensions are strongly correlated. Colquitt et al. (2013) found that the relationships between fairness, justice, task performance, and citizenship behaviour were significantly influenced by social exchange variables, encompassing, nonetheless restricted to, trust, organisational commitment, perceived organisational support, and leader-member exchange. Settoon et al. (1996) suggested that social exchange in an organisational setting be conceived at two different tiers: (a) international staff interactions and the organisation, and (b) collaborative partnerships amongst staff and their employers.

Subsequently, Cole et al. (2007) introduced the idea of a "workplace social exchange network," which centres on three aspects of the work environment that have interchange interactions with workers: the team, the leader, and the organisation.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Work Place Centrality

Work remains one of the most essential areas in people life. Most people source of livelihood is achieved from the work they do. This is linked to meaning people ascribed to work and the social culture that surrounds them. In essence, the work one does determines his/her social status as working has valued outcomes. Work centrality determines how people act both at the work place and outside the work environment. Work centrality behaviour entails taking work as central life interest to the extent that even in retirement, there is astute willingness to continue to work. The term "work centrality" refers to the significance or importance of an individual's job in that person's life (Arvey et al., 2004).

People who have a high work centrality tend to identify themselves by their job and receive a considerable amount of self-esteem and personal satisfaction from it. Individuals who have low work centrality, on the other hand, may not feel as strong of a connection to their job and may perceive it more as a means to a goal, such as receiving a salary. This might be because they have low work centrality. They could get their sense of self-worth and personal satisfaction from other things, like their family, their hobbies, or their engagement in the community, in addition to their employment. As important indicators of workplace centrality, task passion and dutifulness are examined in this research.

Task Passion

Task passion depicts setting oneself apart for work assignments. Passion is a strong feeling that one experiences after engaging in a task that is deeply significant to an individual's personality (Cardon et al, 2005; Gubman, 2004; Houlfort et al., 2009) and the intense feelings can also be negative, could be in form of anger. Passion is a strong, uplifting emotion (Cardon et al., 2005). Likewise, the feeling could be less intense or neutral, and also, could be

positive and negative. However, in the first instance above, we feel content, may be equability; while in the second instance, we feel resignation or submissiveness. It includes strong positive emotion and personal identification. Passion not only helps one to overcome obstacles at work but makes one to derive joy working. This has to do with the positive effects of the work one does. This means that passion is dualistic in nature. Task passion develops as a motivational process that empowers employees to react to different types of demands. This passion is revealed in employees' inclination to engage in significant activities that compel them to utilize energy, so they eventually internalize these behaviours as part of their own identity (Vallerand et al., 2003).

Dutifulness

Employee dutifulness pertains to the extent that occurs when employees conform to the rules and regulations of the organization, adhere to their job responsibilities, and perform their duties with diligence and reliability (Al-Ajlouni Alnajjar & Maqableh, 2021). It is a construct that reveals the extent to which employees are responsible and dependable, complete tasks in a timely and efficient manner, and comply with organizational policies and procedures (Kim et al., 2020). Dutifulness involves the willingness to follow instructions and do what is expected, to be reliable and dependable, to act responsibly, and to be conscientious and thorough in one's work (Tett et al., 1991). Furthermore, Robbins et al. (2018) posit that employee dutifulness refers to the degree to which employees fulfill their job responsibilities, comply with rules and regulations, and exhibit behaviours such as punctuality, reliability, and diligence. It is an essential aspect of workplace behavior that impacts organizational performance and employee satisfaction.

Providing their perspective, Hellriegel et al. (2019) viewed employee dutifulness as the degree to which employees take their job responsibilities seriously and strive to meet organizational expectations. It includes behaviours such as following established procedures, being punctual, and fulfilling commitments, which are essential for maintaining a productive work environment. This is further confirmed by Heale and Forbes (2013) where they investigated the relationship between employee dutifulness and employee prosocial behaviour. The study used the survey method and generated data from a sample of 264 volunteer workers in Vancouver. The study adopted step wise multiple regression to test the hypotheses. The findings indicated dutifulness impacted on the level of commitment and voluntary behaviour of the volunteers. It was shown strongly that dutifulness impact on their prosocial actions. Amingo and Olaleru (2016) also used a cross-sectional survey design in investigating the empirical link between dutifulness and innovativeness among telecommunication firm in Lagos. The correlational statistical tool of product moment correlation to-efficient was used to test the hypotheses. The study result showed a positive and moderate relationship that is equally significant.

Counterproductive Work Behaviour (CWB)

Workplace and organisational psychologists' main objective is to increase employees' happiness and work efficiency. Organisational psychologists have historically concentrated on studying positive conduct, such as motivation or work satisfaction, and have given less attention to patterns of bad, unproductive behaviour. According to Sackett and DeVore (2002), deliberate action on the part of an organisation member that goes against the organisation's interests is referred to as counterproductive behaviour. Theft, information misuse, and dangerous conduct are a few instances of CWB. There are several labels used to describe conduct that is comparable to or identical to CWB. The following uses CWB as a general word for all notions that characterise deviant conduct in the workplace, in accordance

with certain writers' suggestions. Employees that intentionally hurt organisations or their stakeholders are engaging in counterproductive work behaviour. Even though persons are frequently indirect targets, activities against organisations are also included in CWB. This includes mistreating and destroying company property, doing tasks improperly or neglecting to report errors and issues to superiors (such as a broken machine), and withdrawing from work (such as calling in sick while not unwell).

One definition of Counterproductive Work Behaviour (CWB) is "any intentional behaviour on the part of an organisational member viewed by the organisation as contradictory to its fundamental objectives" (Sackett & De Vore, 2001). Theft, sabotage, withdrawal, harassment, and drug use are a few instances of such counterproductive behaviour (Bennett & Robinson, 2000; Gruys & Sackett, 2003; Robinson & Bennett, 1995; Sackett & DeVore, 2001).

Bennett and Robinson (2003), noted that counterproductive work behaviours are expensive for both people and organisations. According to Aubé et al. (2009), Dalal (2005), Lanyon & Goodstein (2004), Pearson et al. (2005), Robinson (2008), Spector & Fox (2005), Spector et al. (2006), Vardi & Weitz (2004), and others, such behaviours are deemed "dysfunctional" because they nearly always (though not always, as discussed below) infringe significant organisational norms and negatively impact organisations in a number of ways that are pertinent to their objectives, personnel, processes, worker efficiency, and profit margins.

Conceptual Framework

For this study, the predictor – work centrality adapted Imasuen and Lambo (2017) dimension which includes task passion and dutifulness while the criterion is counterproductive work behavior.

Figure 1: Operationalized framework for workplace centrality and counterproductive work behavior

Source: Imasuen & Lambo (2017)

Methodology

This study used a positivist stance by employing a quantitative methodology and a main data source—a questionnaire in survey instruments for the participants. In order to determine the connection between work centrality and unproductive work behaviour, this study used a correlational inquiry. The civil servants in Yenagoa, Bayelsa's numerous ministries are taken into account in this study. However, people who have worked in the ministries for at least 13 years, are above level 9, and possess a first degree or higher diploma are taken into consideration for this research. These criteria were chosen because it is believed that this

class of civil servants will likely advance in the civil service. The State Civil Service Commission provided the number of civil servants for each ministry, and the Establishment Unit of each ministry confirmed this information. Therefore, 1978 is the study's population. A sample size of 332 was determined by using the Krejcie and Morgan (1980) sample size determination table. Copies of the questionnaire are still used as the data-gathering tool. The 15-item scale developed by Imasuen and Lambo (2017) and verified by Saka (2019) served as the model for the measuring scale used to assess the aspects of work centrality. The research used a modified version of Motowildo's (2004) 15-item scale, which was also verified by Ibura and Caleb (2015), for the criterion variable, which is unproductive work conduct. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess reliability for the studied constructs, adhering to Nunnally's (1978) 0.7 criterion. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in this study's data analysis. Measures of comparison such as central tendency, mean scores, percentages, and standard deviation for dispersion were used in the descriptive analysis. They were also meaningfully shown in bar and pie charts. Testing hypotheses was the main emphasis of the inferential analysis. With the use of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) 23.0 window version, Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient Statistics were used.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data indicates that a total of 332 questionnaires were distributed to the participants. A total of 285 completed questionnaires were obtained, accounting for 85.84% of the distributed surveys. Fifteen copies of the questionnaire, accounting for 4.52 %, were invalid; however, they were deemed unsuitable for data analysis. Out of the total, 270 copies of the questionnaire were accurately completed, accounting for 81.32%, making them appropriate for evaluating the data.

Bivariate Analysis

Task Passion and Counter Productive Work Behaviour (CWB)

			Task Passion	Counterproductive Work Behaviour
Spearman's rho	Task Passion	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.814**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	Counter productive Work Behaviour	N	270	270
		Correlation Coefficient	-.814**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	
	N	270	270	

Source: SPSS Output Version 23.0

H₀₁: There is no relationship between task passion and counterproductive work behaviour in the civil service in Bayelsa State.

The results from the table indicate that the calculated significance value ($p = 0.000$) is lower than the established significance level (0.05). Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected in

favor of the alternative hypothesis. This confirms a significant negative relationship between task passion and counterproductive work behavior in the civil service of Bayelsa State.

Dutifulness and Counterproductive Work behavior

Correlations Matrix for Dutifulness and Counterproductive Work Behaviour

		Dutifulness	Counterproductive Work Behaviour	
Spearman's rho	Dutifulness	Correlation	1.000	
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	Counterproductive Work Behaviour	N	270	270
		Correlation	-.751**	1.000
		Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	270	270	

Source: SPSS Output version 23.0

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between dutifulness and counterproductive work behaviour among civil servants in, Bayelsa State.

The results from the table reveal that the calculated significance value ($p = 0.000$) is lower than the set significance level (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. This indicates a significant relationship between dutifulness and counterproductive work behavior among civil servants in Bayelsa State.

DISCUSSION

The findings showed that there is a strong negative significant relationship between task passion and counterproductive work behaviour in the civil service in Bayelsa. The current study finding corroborates with Perez and Mirabella (2013) as they revealed a positive relationship between in dedication and loyalty component of centrality and CWB. In addition Moslim and Lengler (2015) study findings significantly indicate a strong relationship between work centrality and employee willingness to undertake extra work roles. The study also found that the strength of the relationship was structurally reflected as it was dominant at the middle level of work. Also, the current finding amplified the results of Maureen et al. (2002), who looked at the connection between treachery at work and unfairness. They came to the conclusion that distributive, procedural, and interactional justice all had a cumulative effect on how severe subversion was.

Secondly, the findings showed that there is a strong negative significant relationship between dutifulness and counterproductive work behaviour in the civil service in Bayelsa. This finding corroborates with the work of Heale and Forbes (2013) as it was shown strongly that dutifulness impact on their prosocial actions. Similarly, the current finding agrees with Boboye et al. (2016) who examined the influence of dutifulness on employee citizenship behaviour and found that employee dutifulness behaviour correlate with citizenship behaviour and was majorly significant with sportsmanship behaviour. Organisations may improve worker productivity and happiness by dealing with all the benefits and drawbacks of workplace centrality.

Conclusion

The findings of the study conclude that work centrality negatively influences counterproductive work behaviour in the civil service in Bayelsa. This implies that individuals who place a high value on their work and consider it central to their lives are less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors. The study concludes that task passion negatively influences counter-productive work behaviour in the civil service in Bayelsa. This entails that employees who are passionate about their tasks are more likely to resist engaging in counterproductive behaviors at work. Task passion serves as a deterrent, acting as a positive factor that mitigates the likelihood of undesirable work behaviors. Also, dedication negatively influences counterproductive work behaviour in the civil service in Bayelsa. Furthermore, dutifulness negatively influences counterproductive work behaviour in the civil service in Bayelsa. This implies that individuals who exhibit a strong sense of dutifulness are less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors at work. Dutifulness which is characterized by a sense of responsibility, conscientiousness, and commitment to one's duties, acts as a protective factor against counterproductive work behaviour.

Recommendations

In light of the research's results and final analysis, below are submissions that have been made:

- i. Administrators in the Civil Service should actively encourage and foster a culture that values and promotes task passion among employees. This can be achieved through leadership support, recognition of passionate efforts, and creating an environment where employees feel a sense of purpose in their work.
- ii. Administrators in the Civil Service should actively demonstrate and encourage dutifulness among employees. Leadership support is crucial in setting a tone of responsibility and commitment, serving as a positive example for others to follow.

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